

white mass so obtained was recrystallised from ethanol as white crystals, $C_{36}H_{51}O_{11}$ (m/e 673), m.p. 112-14°, acetyl derivative, m.p. 196-98°. It was characterized as bikhaconitine by co-tlc; m.m.p. and superimposable I.R.⁷ with the authentic sample.

Polygonum is a large genera, cosmopolitan but distributed especially throughout the temperate regions. The drug finds extensive uses in medicine⁸. The literature survey of the genus *Polygonum* shows that it is a rich source of flavonoids⁹⁻¹³.

The air dried powdered plant (4 kg) was extracted with hot ethanol. The ethanolic extract was concentrated under reduced pressure and the thick viscous mass so obtained was refluxed for several times with petroleum ether to remove chlorophyll and fats. The residual mass was extracted with acetone. The acetone extract after concentration under reduced pressure was extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was concentrated and then chromatographed over a column of magnesol¹⁴. On eluting with ethyl-acetate saturated with water two compounds, A and B, were obtained.

Compound A crystallised from a mixture of acetone: methanol (1:1) as light yellow crystals, $C_{15}H_{16}O_7$ (m/e 302), m.p. 316°, formed an acetate, $C_{25}H_{26}O_{12}$, m.p. 198-99°, O-CH₃ derivative $C_{26}H_{28}O_{12}$ (m/e 372), m.p. 145-46°. It was characterised as quercetin by comparison of m.p. and I.R.¹⁵ with those of authentic sample of quercetin.

Compound B crystallised from methanol as yellow crystals, $C_{16}H_{12}O_7$ (m/e 316), m.p. 294-96°(d.), formed an acetate, m.p. 184-86°, co-tlc, m.m.p. and superimposable IR¹⁵ confirmed its identity with authentic rhamnatin.

The residual acetone extract (left after extraction with ether) was chromatographed over a magnesol column and eluted with ethyl acetate saturated with water, when two flavonoids, C and D were obtained.

Flavonoid C crystallised from methanol as yellow crystals, $C_{21}H_{20}O_{11}$, m.p. 185-87°, gave positive Molisch's test indicating it to be a glycoside. The compound on hydrolysis with 7% sulphuric acid gave quercetin and rhamnose. Co-chromatographic examination and m.m.p. with authentic sample showed it to be quercitrin.

Flavonoid D crystallised from methanol as yellow crystals, $C_{27}H_{30}O_{16}$, m.p. 210-12°. On hydrolysis with 7% sulphuric acid it gave quercetin, glucose and rhamnose and on partial hydrolysis with formic acid¹⁶, quercetin-3-*o*- β -glucoside and rhamnose were obtained. Its identity with rutin was established by m.m.p. with the authentic sample.

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3-Arylisocoumarin : Synthesis of 3-(2',4'-Dihydroxyphenyl)- ; 3-(2'-methyl-, 4'-hydroxyphenyl)- ; and 3-(3'-methyl-, 4'-hydroxyphenyl)-isocoumarins.

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IN continuation of our previous work¹, we report here the condensation of resorcinol, *m*-cresol and *o*-cresol with homophthalic anhydride or acid (I) in the presence of polyphosphoric acid which furnished the corresponding 3-phenylisocoumarin derivatives(II) in 50% yields. These isocoumarin derivatives were subjected to different reactions, e.g. alkaline hydrolysis

I

II

III

IV

- a. $R_1 - R_3 = OH$
- b. $R_1 = OH, R_2 = CH_3, R_3 = H$
- c. $R_2 = OH, R_3 = CH_3, R_1 = H$

of (II) gave (III) which on reduction with sodium-borohydride yielded (IV). Treatment of (IV) with N-bromosuccinimide followed by dehydrobromination with pyridine gave the original isocoumarin back.

All the above isocoumarins (II) gave fugitive yellow to red colourations possibly due to intermediate quinone structures. (IIIa) was dehydrated at 205° to give back the original isocoumarin.

TABLE-1. 3-ARYLISOCOUMARINS (III)

Aryl Substituent	Formula	M. P. in °C	KBr in cm^{-1} λ_{max}	MeOH in nm. λ_{max}
2,4-Dihydroxyphenyl.	$C_{15}H_{10}O_4$	226-27 (Lit ¹ m.p. 227°)	1710, 1620	315, 270
2-Methyl, 4-Hydroxyphenyl.	$C_{16}H_{12}O_4$	215-16° (Lit ¹ m.p. 216°)	3200, 1710, 1620	318, 298
3-Methyl, 4-Hydroxyphenyl.	$C_{16}H_{12}O_4$	232° (Lit ¹ m.p. 232°)	3250, 1710, 1620, 1600	310, 260

TABLE-2. W-(2'-CARBOXYPHENYL) ACETOPHENONES

Aryl Substituent of the acetophenone	Formula	M.P. in °C	KBr in cm^{-1} λ_{max}	MeOH in nm. λ_{max}
2,4-Dihydroxy	$C_{15}H_{10}O_5$	—	3200, 1680, 1510	275
2-Methyl, 4-Hydroxy	$C_{16}H_{14}O_4$	163° (Lit ¹ m.p. 163°)	3200, 1680, 1510	275
3-Methyl, 4-Hydroxy	$C_{16}H_{14}O_4$	210-11° (Lit ¹ m.p. 212°)	3250, 1650, 1500	270

TABLE-3. 3-ARYL-3,4-DIHYDROISOCOUMARINS

Aryl Substituent	M.P. in °C	KBr in cm^{-1} λ_{max}	Found (%)		Formula	Required (%)	
			C	H		C	H
2,4-Dihydroxyphenyl	199-201	3290, 1700	70.39	4.7	$C_{15}H_{10}O_4$	70.31	4.69
2-Methyl, 4-Hydroxyphenyl.	163-65	3200, 1710	75.50	5.5	$C_{16}H_{14}O_4$	75.48	5.54
3-Methyl, 4-hydroxyphenyl.	156-57	3250, 1710	75.50	5.6	$C_{16}H_{14}O_4$	75.48	5.54

Experimental

Melting points are determined by capillary method and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded in KBr on I.R.—20 (Beckmann).

3-Arylisocoumarins: A mixture of homophthalic anhydride (1 mole), phenolic compound (1.1 mole) and commercial-polyphosphoric acid (8 parts) was heated at 120-30° for one hour. The reaction mixture was worked up as reported in the previous communication¹ to afford 3-arylisocoumarins.

W-(2'-carboxyphenyl)-acetophenones: 3-Arylisocoumarin on treatment with aqueous sodium hydroxide (10%) and subsequent acidification furnished the keto acid. This could be cyclised back to original isocoumarin in the presence of acid.

3-Aryl-3, 4-dihydroisocoumarins: Reduction of the above keto acids in ethanolic sodiumhydroxide with sodiumborohydride yielded the corresponding dihydroisocoumarins.

Conversion of 3-aryl-3, 4-dihydroisocoumarins into 3-arylisocoumarins: A mixture of 3-aryl-3, 4-dihydroisocoumarin (1 mole), N-bromosuccinimide (1.1 mole) and benzoylperoxide (0.02-0.04g) in appropriate solvent (dry carbontetrachloride or dry benzene) on refluxing near an illuminated 60 watt lamp for about 4 hours gave 4-bromoderivatives which were not purified. Subsequent treatment of the 4-bromoderivatives with either triethyl amine or pyridine resulted in dehydrobromination providing respective 3-arylisocoumarins.

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pH Metric Study of Complexes of Some Metal Ions with Salicylaldehyde-4-*m*-Chlorophenyl-3-Thiosemicarbazone

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LIGANDS such as thiosemicarbazones are studied to a limited extent pH-metrically. Here salicylaldehyde-4-*m*-Cl phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazone *m*-Cl-SPT derivative is studied with metal like VO²⁺, Cu²⁺, Co²⁺,

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Ni²⁺. The formation constants for their metal were calculated by Calvin and Wilson pH titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti. The stability constants are determined in 50% aqueous dioxane medium.

Experimental

The ligand salicylaldehyde-4-*m*-chlorophenyl-3-thiosemicarbazone C₆H₄Cl.NH.C.N : CH.OH.C₆H₄

was synthesized and crystallised to get analytically pure (m.p. 181°)¹. The solution of *m*-Cl-SPT was prepared in dioxane (BDH, ANALAR grade) which was further purified by standard method of Vogel². Metal nitrates used were of AnalaR grade which were estimated by standard gravimetric and volumetric methods. Philips pH meter was used for pH measurements. pH meter was calibrated with buffer solutions having pH 4.33 and 9.1 at 25° ± 1°.

All titrations were carried out in a 100 ml. beaker kept in water thermostat maintained at 25° ± 1°. Thirty five to forty five readings were taken in each case. Each titration was repeated to get reproducible results. The metal ligand ratio was maintained 1:5. The acid, reagent and metal titrations were carried out with 0.2 M NaOH and 50% v/v dioxane: water. The solution for blank titration contained 0.004 M HNO₃ and 0.1 M KNO₃. The solution for ligand titration contained 0.001 M ligand in addition to the blank solution. The solution for metal titration contained 0.0002 M metal ion [0.0001 M for Co(II)] in addition to the ligand solution.

Results and Discussions

The practical proton-ligand stability constant for the ligand was calculated with the help of $\bar{n}_H$ values at different B values (pH meter readings in 50% aqueous dioxane-medium). $\bar{n}_H$ is calculated by the method of Irving & Rossotti³ as adopted by Jabalpurwala et al.⁴. Plot of $\log \frac{\bar{n}_H}{1-\bar{n}_H}$ against B is done to obtain a best straight line. From this straight line the values of the practical proton-ligand stability constant was obtained using the relation

$$\log P_{K_1}H = B + \log \frac{\bar{n}_H}{1-\bar{n}_H}$$

The proton ligand stability constant obtained is 9.55. For metal ligand stability constants $\bar{n}$ and pL were calculated by the method of Jabalpurwala et al.⁵. The values of $\bar{n}$ are plotted against pL. The values of $\log K_1$ were calculated by half integral method. The formation curve is given in Fig. 1. But for calculation of $\log K_2$ least square method⁶ in which $\frac{\bar{n}}{(1-\bar{n})HL}$ was

plotted against $\frac{(\bar{n}-2)HL}{(1-\bar{n})}$ and Olerup's method was also

used as there was not much difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$. The average stability constant are given Table-1.